

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

Identifying the Distinctive Features of a Psychologist's Communicative Competence

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Abstract

This article explores various approaches to the study of communicative competence, particularly the communicative, normative, and semantic dimensions. It evaluates the level of development of communicative competence in psychologists. The use of communicative methods in the teaching of psychological disciplines enhances the speaker's cognitive engagement and contributes to the development of key communicative qualities of speech.

Keywords: communicative competence, educational psychologist, counseling psychologist, organizational psychologist, psychology lecturer, communicative features of speech, clarity, logical coherence, expressiveness, communicative method.

Effective communication is one of the primary factors contributing to the efficiency of human activity, successful socialization, and the achievement of life goals. The ancient Greek philosopher Socrates once said, "Speak to me and I will tell you who you are." A person's intellect, character, emotions, goals, interests, and needs are manifested—either directly or indirectly—through the way and content of their speech. A defining feature of a psychologist's professional activity is the ability to "see the other," to understand psychological issues, and to assist in their resolution by utilizing specific speech markers during interactions. Additionally, the nature of a psychologist's profession—as a teacher, counselor, organizational consultant, or academic—also influences both their general communicative competence and individual linguistic style.

General communicative competence is characterized by communicative qualities such as meaningfulness, literacy, logical consistency, politeness, correctness, and clarity. The use of particular qualities depends on the specific professional function of the psychologist. For instance, a counseling psychologist's speech must be accessible, comprehensible, persuasive, and flexible; a psychology lecturer should speak clearly, knowledgeably, and convincingly while using illustrative examples; and an organizational psychologist must be fluent in both the structural dynamics of the organization and its professional terminology.

Recent studies increasingly focus on the acoustic and dynamic properties of speech, particularly within the context of digitalized learning environments and the integration of information and communication technologies. Factors such as speech fluency, pace, and information density are gaining importance.

Oral speech—whether logical or disorganized, fluent or interrupted, accurate or flawed—often provides greater insight into a person's character than the message being conveyed. The speed of speech also plays a crucial role. A psychologist's communicative competence is shaped by the ability to select appropriate speech genres and functional styles for communicative situations, and to apply communicative principles effectively. This represents a unique form of verbal and written expression of ideas, grounded in general knowledge and intellect.

The close relationship between thought and speech implies that the development of one directly affects the other. That is, the level of speech development reflects the level of cognitive development, and vice versa. Communicative competence is an integral component of one's overall cultural competency.

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From a psycholinguistic perspective, communicative competence can be divided into its normative, communicative, and ethical dimensions. Accordingly, the concept of communicative competence can be approached from multiple theoretical angles.

Communicative competence is first and foremost viewed as a culture of communication, encompassing a system of interrelated communicative features. These features can be systematized and conceptualized through the interplay between language as a symbolic system, cognition, consciousness, the communication partner, and the situational context. Given the importance of communicative effectiveness, the linguistic structure of speech as a medium of influence becomes the main subject of communicative competence.

Synthesizing various viewpoints on the subject, we may conclude that the methodological foundation of communicative competence lies in the theoretical substantiation of its communicative features as evaluative criteria. These features include both spoken and written speech traits that ensure communicative efficiency and mutual understanding among interlocutors. Within a systematic framework, B.N. Golovin identified key communicative features: correctness, purity, clarity, logicity, expressiveness, richness, relevance, imagery (closely related to expressiveness), practicality, and persuasiveness.

In professional settings, the communicative features of speech reflect the level of education and skill development in that field. The integration of normativity, content, and expressiveness ensures its effectiveness, giving rise to what is referred to as “professional communicative competence.”

To evaluate the development level of communicative competence, a study was conducted involving 157 psychology students at Maxim Tank Belarusian State Pedagogical University. The research method was a semi-structured targeted interview that included several questions about the expected characteristics of a psychologist’s professional speech.

Responses were recorded digitally and subsequently transcribed. The identified communicative qualities were categorized into specific groups: Content (reasoning, informativeness, clarity, literacy, logicity, use of descriptive tools); Clarity (comprehensibility); Expressiveness (volume, fluency, preparedness, intonational variation); Persuasiveness (purity, precision).

Difficulties in speech production often stem from issues related to correctness and argumentation. Some students neglect the acquisition of professional terminology, deeming it unnecessary, which results in a lack of clarity. A well-developed ability to debate and justify opinions using acquired knowledge, skills, facts, and examples is essential for effective professional communication.

A client-oriented and professional communication style fosters the most effective interaction between a psychologist and a client by focusing on the emotional responses of the latter.

The high levels of speech comprehensibility observed in the study suggest that most participants do not exhibit articulation deficiencies. As a type of speech activity, articulation also entails a mechanical process of accurate sound production. A psychologist’s speech should be attention-grabbing, clear, and articulated with good diction, thus encouraging openness in conversation. Conversely, pronunciation irregularities may distract the listener from the message and negatively affect the overall quality of communication.

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Oral speech, characterized by externally perceivable features, is formed through auditory language tools in real-time interactions. It is often considered more difficult to replicate as it emerges in the moment of cognitive processing. The time available for structuring the message and selecting precise words is significantly reduced in spoken discourse.

Spoken language allows for real-time corrections, reformulations, and clarification of specific constructions, depending on the interlocutor's verbal or nonverbal feedback. This makes it possible to elaborate on unclear points, omit the obvious, or simplify complex expressions. Additionally, third-party evaluations of a psychologist's speech promote critical self-assessment and self-improvement.

Conclusion

A high level of professional communicative competence in a psychologist is a reflection of intellectual maturity and professional competence. It requires adherence to various academic and communicative standards tied to the level of professional education.

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